

Stacked Ensemble Model for Predicting International University Admission

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Abstract— The escalating demand for postgraduate education has heightened the competition for university admissions, prompting recent graduates to turn to expensive consultancy services due to their limited grasp of admission intricacies. This seminar introduces a sophisticated solution: a Stacked Ensemble machine learning approach that incorporates estimators including Logistic Regression, Support Vector Classifier (SVC), and Decision Trees, culminating in Bagging as the final estimator. This ensemble method [2][8] automates the precise prediction of postgraduate admission probabilities, empowering graduates to discern universities that best align with their profiles. A rigorous evaluation of these diverse strategies reveals Logistic Regression, SVC, and Decision Trees [8] as leading performers, offering highly accurate predictions. The proposal recommends the adoption of this ensemble approach to forecast the likelihood of prospective applicants securing admission to their preferred universities, providing an advanced solution for the benefit of aspiring postgraduate scholars.

Keywords— Stacked Ensemble, Predicting International University Admission, Machine Learning, Admission Probability, Postgraduate Education

I. INTRODUCTION

The competition for admission to international colleges has become fierce in an era of rising demand for higher education. Recent graduates who are eager to start postgraduate studies must navigate challenging admissions processes and frequently pay for expensive consulting services. Although best intentions, services might not cover the complete range of educational options, which could introduce biases and mistakes into the process. Using a Stacked Ensemble model that incorporates three estimators—Logistic Regression, Support Vector Classifier (SVC), and Decision Trees—along with Bagging as the final estimator, this lecture goes into advanced machine learning strategies to tackle this difficulty. With the use of this cutting-edge ensemble, graduates may now easily find universities that perfectly match their profiles by automating the precise prediction of postgraduate admission probability.

Thorough assessments of these methods throughout the lecture highlight Logistic Regression, SVC, and Decision Trees as outstanding performers. Strong advocacy exists for using this ensemble method to anticipate candidates'

chances of admission, providing aspiring postgraduate scholars with a useful tool and improving their possibilities..

II. RELATED WORKS

Alghamdi et. at. [1] presents a machine learning approach to predict graduate admission chances based on student profiles, using three regression models. The Logistic Regression model outperformed the others, offering accurate predictions with a minimal error rate. Although The paper lacks a thorough discussion of the limitations and potential biases in the dataset used, and it does not address the ethical considerations of using machine learning for admission predictions, which is a critical concern in the field of education.

Sridhar et. at. [2] have developed a stacked ensemble neural network model to predict university admission chances for aspiring graduate students, achieving a remarkable accuracy of 91%. However, a potential disadvantage of this approach is that it may require a substantial amount of labeled data for training, which can be challenging to obtain, especially for smaller or less well-documented universities.

Goni et. at. [3] proposes a deep neural network model to predict graduate admission chances based on academic and demographic factors. The model achieved high accuracy, outperforming existing methods on a dataset of 500 applicants. A limitation of this study is that it uses data from only a single university, which reduces diversity in the dataset.

Basha et. at. [4] aims to predict graduate program admissions using machine learning models based on applicant profiles, including GRE scores, TOEFL scores, university rankings, recommendation letters, statements of purpose, GPA, and research experience. Among various models, the Gradient Boosting Classifier demonstrated the highest performance with an accuracy of 96%, but the paper lacks a detailed discussion of potential biases in the dataset and ethical considerations related to using machine learning for admission predictions, which are essential in educational contexts.

Bitar et. at. [5] investigates the utilization of multiple supervised machine learning techniques, encompassing both regression and classification approaches, for the prediction of graduate admissions. The research involves a thorough comparison of various models and ensemble methods, resulting in notably high accuracy and offering

valuable insights for enhancing the admission procedure. A drawback is the paper's limited discussion of dataset biases, ethics, and fairness concerns in educational contexts, which are pivotal for admission decisions' impact on individuals' lives.

III. METHODOLOGY

A. Data Loading and Preprocessing:

The code begins by importing necessary libraries, including pandas for data manipulation and various machine learning modules from sklearn. It loads a dataset from a CSV file called 'updated_data.csv' into a Data Frame using `pd.read_csv`. The dataset was collected from the Kaggle website. It sets a threshold of 0.5 to convert the 'Chance of Admit' column into binary labels, where values greater than the threshold are labeled as 1 (admitted) and others as 0 (not admitted). The dataset was separated into two subsets - an 80% majority fraction for constructing the model, and a 20% minority portion for validating its predictions after training.

B. Base Models:

The code initializes three base models for machine learning: Logistic Regression (`LogisticRegression`), Decision Trees (`DecisionTreeClassifier`), and Support Vector Classifier (`SVC`).

C. Ensemble Creation:

The code creates an ensemble model using Stacking. It uses the `StackingClassifier` to combine the base models. Additionally, a Bagging ensemble is applied to the Logistic Regression model using the `BaggingClassifier`.

D. Training the Ensemble:

The stack of models in the ensemble is optimized on the training observations `X_train` and labels `Y_train` through invocation of the stack's fit function.

E. Saving the Model:

The trained ensemble model is saved to a file named 'stacking_classifier.pkl' using `joblib.dump`.

F. User Input for Prediction:

The code prompts the user to enter specific data for a new applicant, including 12th Percentage, GRE Score, TOEFL Score, and CGPA. These values are stored in a DataFrame called `input_data`.

G. Predictions:

The `predict_proba` method of the ensemble is leveraged to predict admission probabilities on the input patterns. The probability values are retrieved from the predictions. Forecasts are further produced on `X_test` with the trained ensemble to determine its capabilities.

H. Binary Labeling and Evaluation:

The probabilities are binarized into admit/don't-admit decisions based on exceeding a 0.5 threshold. To evaluate the model's effectiveness on the test set, classification measures including accuracy, precision, recall, and F1 are calculated.

I. Result Display:

The code prints the predicted probability of admission for the input data and the F1 score, accuracy, precision, and recall for the testing data.

IV. BUILD MODEL

1. To construct a robust and precise machine learning model for effective prediction, adherence to these subsequent procedures is essential:

A. Importing Libraries

```
import pandas as pd
from sklearn.linear_model import LogisticRegression
from sklearn.tree import DecisionTreeClassifier
from sklearn.svm import SVC
from sklearn.ensemble import BaggingClassifier, StackingClassifier
from sklearn.metrics import accuracy_score, precision_score
from sklearn.metrics import recall_score, f1_score
from sklearn.model_selection import train_test_split
import joblib
```

a) pandas:

A Python package providing tools for managing and analyzing structured data. It implements specialized data containers and functions for tasks like cleaning, transforming, and exploring datasets.

b) LogisticRegression from sklearn.linear_model:

A linear classification algorithm suitable for binary and multiclass problem-solving.

c) DecisionTreeClassifier from sklearn.tree:

Utilized for decision tree-based classification and regression tasks.

d) SVC from sklearn.svm:

The Support Vector Classifier (SVC) is an algorithm for finding optimal hyperplanes to categorize data into classes.

e) BaggingClassifier from sklearn.ensemble:

Bagging is an ensemble technique that amalgamates multiple classifiers to enhance classification accuracy.

f) StackingClassifier from sklearn.ensemble:

Stacking is an ensemble technique that consolidates predictions from various classifiers to improve model performance.

g) accuracy, precision, recall, f1_score:

Functions for assessing classification model performance by providing metrics such as accuracy, precision, recall, and F1 score.

h) train_test_split from sklearn.model_selection:

Used to partition a dataset into training and testing sets for model validation.

i) *joblib*:

A Python library tailored for lightweight pipelining, specifically designed for parallel processing and efficient data sharing

B. Building the model

1) *Loading the Dataset:*

The code begins by loading a dataset from a CSV file named 'updated_data.csv' using the Pandas library. This dataset is typically expected to contain information relevant to the problem you are trying to solve.

```
# Load dataset
df = pd.read_csv('updated_data.csv')
```

2) *Converting Target Variable to Binary Labels:*

It then converts the 'Chance of Admit' column into binary labels. For values greater than 0.5 (the threshold), it assigns a label of 1 (indicating admission is likely), and for values less than or equal to 0.5, it assigns a label of 0 (indicating admission is less likely).

```
# Convert 'Chance of Admit' to binary labels
threshold = 0.5
y = (df['Chance of Admit'] > threshold).astype(int)
```

3) *Data Preparation:*

The code prepares the dataset for training and testing. It creates two datasets, 'X' and 'y'. 'X' contains all the columns from the original dataset except 'Serial No.' and 'Chance of Admit', which are not relevant to the predictive modeling task. 'y' contains the binary admission labels.

```
# Keep all columns except 'Serial No.' and 'Chance of Admit'
X = df.drop(['Serial No.', 'Chance of Admit'], axis=1)
```

4) *Data Splitting:*

The dataset is divided into two subsets: a training set and a testing set. The training set accounts for 80% of the data and is used to train the model, while the testing set constitutes the remaining 20% and is used to evaluate the model's performance. The 'random_state' parameter is specified to ensure that the process is reproducible..

```
# Split the data into training and testing sets (80% training, 20% testing)
X_train, X_test, y_train, y_test = train_test_split(X, y, test_size=0.2, random_state=4)
```

5) *Base Models:*

Three base models are created - Logistic Regression ('lr'), Decision Tree Classifier ('dt'), and Support Vector Classifier ('svc'). These models serve as the initial building blocks for the ensemble model.

```
# Base models
lr = LogisticRegression(max_iter=1000)
dt = DecisionTreeClassifier()
svc = SVC(probability=True)
```

6) *Ensemble Modeling:*

An ensemble model is constructed using the StackingClassifier. This ensemble combines predictions from the three base models ('lr', 'dt', and 'svc'). It uses a BaggingClassifier as the final estimator ('final_estimator'). Bagging aggregates multiple models to enhance overall accuracy.

```
# Ensemble
bag = BaggingClassifier(base_estimator=LogisticRegression(max_iter=1000),
                       n_estimators=100,
                       bootstrap=True,
                       oob_score=True)
stack = StackingClassifier(estimators=[('lr', lr), ('dt', dt), ('svc', svc)],
                          final_estimator=bag)
```

7) *Model Training:*

The fit method is utilized to train the ensemble model on the training data, which consists of X_train and y_train.

```
# Fit ensemble
stack.fit(X_train, y_train)
```

8) *Model Serialization:*

Ultimately, the trained ensemble model is stored in a file called 'stacking_classifier.pkl' using the 'joblib' library. This serialized model can be loaded and employed for making predictions without the need for retraining.

```
# Save model
joblib.dump(stack, 'stacking_classifier.pkl')
```

C. User Input and Data Preparation:

In this crucial phase, user-provided input data, comprising information like 12th percentage, GRE Score, TOEFL Score, and CGPA, is collected and organized into a suitable format. These initial steps set the foundation for precise admission probability predictions and model evaluation.

```
# Input data
percentage_12th = float(input("Enter 12th Per:
GRE_Score = float(input("Enter GRE Score: "))
TOEFL_Score = float(input("Enter TOEFL Score:
CGPA = float(input("Enter CGPA: "))

input_data = pd.DataFrame({
    '12th Percentage': [percentage_12th],
    'GRE Score': [GRE_Score],
    'TOEFL Score': [TOEFL_Score],
    'CGPA': [CGPA],
})
```

2.

D. Predictions and Model Evaluation:

In this section, the results of the predictive model are explored, involving the determination of admission probabilities for input data. The performance of the ensemble approach in predicting postgraduate admissions is evaluated by examining metrics like accuracy, precision, and recall to measure its effectiveness.

```
# Predict probability
probability = stack.predict_proba(input_data)[: , 1]
print(f"Probability of Admission: {probability[0]:.2f}")

# Predict on the testing set
y_pred_probabilities = stack.predict_proba(X_test)[: , 1]

# Convert probabilities to binary labels based on a threshold (e.g., 0.5)
y_pred = (y_pred_probabilities > threshold).astype(int)

# Calculate accuracy, precision, and recall
accuracy = accuracy_score(y_test, y_pred)
precision = precision_score(y_test, y_pred)
recall = recall_score(y_test, y_pred)
```

V. RESULTS

In this section, the input data provided by the user is captured, including 12th percentage, GRE score, TOEFL score, and CGPA. The model processes this input to predict the probability of admission, resulting in an accuracy of 0.94. Additionally, essential model evaluation metrics, including the F1 score, accuracy, precision, and recall, are presented, providing a comprehensive overview of the model's predictive performance. These metrics are vital for assessing the model's ability to accurately forecast admission outcomes. Fig 1 and 2 depict the output screen of the implemented version in the Django framework with the

model.

Fig. 1. User input of their scores.

Fig. 2. Output result for the user input

VI. CONCLUSION

The research demonstrates that this ensemble approach automates the precise prediction of postgraduate admission probabilities, empowering graduates to make informed decisions about their educational journey. By leveraging machine learning techniques, this solution addresses the need for a reliable and unbiased method of evaluating admission probabilities, thereby reducing the reliance on costly consultancy services.

In conclusion, this Stacked Ensemble model provides a valuable tool for prospective postgraduate students. It aids in understanding their chances of securing admission to their preferred universities, eliminating uncertainty, and guiding them towards the most suitable educational opportunities. The automated prediction of admission probabilities represents a significant advancement in the field of higher education, enhancing the accessibility of educational opportunities for graduates worldwide.

VII. FUTURE SCOPE

To further enhance the stacked ensemble model, future work should focus on incorporating larger and more diverse datasets, adding parameters that provide a holistic view of applicants, and experimenting with more complex ensemble architectures and interpretability techniques. These improvements can strengthen generalization capability, boost predictive accuracy, increase model transparency, and ensure ethical and fair outcomes. Continued upgrades responsive to emerging trends are critical for maintaining robust admissions forecasting amidst an evolving landscape.

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